

TYPES OF INTERNET COMMENTS BY EVALUATIVE NATURE

Ismoilova Odina A'zamjon qizi

Andijan State University 2nd year doctoral (Phd) student

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15738934>

Abstract: This article researches the internal classification of Internet comments according to their evaluative nature, the tools that implement the evaluative action, and the specific features of trolling comments in a communicative situation.

Keywords: computer linguistics, Internet comments, classification, subject, object, basis, standard, illocutionary and perlocutionary aspects, emoji, gifs, and memes.

In the 21st century, linguistics has developed significantly and has set itself new problems. One of these problems is the study of the language system based on an anthropocentric approach. While the anthropocentric approach to language studies the role of the human factor in language and its direct participation in the communication process, the development of science has led to the emergence of new areas such as cognitive linguistics, linguoculturology, neurolinguistics, sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, pragmalinguistics, ethnolinguistics, linguopoetics, associative linguistics and computer linguistics. Internet comments, which are the focus of our study, are also directly related to the issue of the personal factor in the areas of today's anthropocentric linguistics.

In today's integrated digital information age, with the transformation of the world of social networks into a communicative space, the need to observe and analyze the specific discursive practice of the global information network is increasing. The volume of scientific work on the linguistic features of Internet communication is progressing. These include research works by a number of researchers such as Sh.Shahobiddinova, Sh.Yuldasheva¹, D.Rustamov², U.Mahmudova³ in Uzbek linguistics and A.S.Trach⁴, N.V.Zudilina⁵, A.V.Vovkula⁶, L.Yu.Shipitsina⁷, Irina Topchii⁸, E.N.Zemlyanskaya, N.M.Koroleva⁹ in world linguistics.

¹ Ш. Ҳ.Шаҳобиддинова, Ш.Х. Юлдашева “Интернет мулоқот ва унинг тадқиқига доир айрим мулоҳазалар” Илмий хабарнома, АДУ, №2 2018th year. 85-88- pages.

² Д.А.Рустамов “Интернет мулоқотининг ўзига хос жиҳатлари” Сўз санъати халқаро журнали | Международный журнал искусство слова | International journal of word art №3 | 2020. 213-220- p.

³ U.U.Mahmudova “Ijtimoiy tarmoq diskursining xususiyatlari” Ta’limda raqamli texnologiyalarni tadbiq etishning zamonaviy tendensiyalari va rivojlanish omillari Conference Proceedings No. 39, Volume 1, January 2025, pages 45-51.

⁴ А.С.Трач “Особенности использования письменной речи в сети интернет” Известия ЮФУ. Технические науки. С: 34-39. <file:///C:/Users/i7/OneDrive/Desktop/osobennosti-ispolzovaniya-pismennoy-rechi-v-seti-internet.pdf>. Retrieved on: 19.05.2025.

⁵ Н.В.Зудилина “Особенности проявления интерактивности интернет-сообществ” Ученые записки Таврического национального университета им. В.И. Вернадского Серия «Философия. Культурология. Политология. Социология». Том 24 (63). 2011. № 3-4. С. 143-152. <file:///C:/Users/i7/OneDrive/Desktop/osobennosti-proyavleniya-interaktivnosti-internet-soobschestv.pdf>.

⁶ А.В.Вовкула “Интерактивная форма коммуникации в медиадискурсе”. Вестник Челябинского государственного университета. 2015. № 10 (365). Филология. Искусствоведение. Вып. 95. С. 32–38.

⁷ Л. Ю. Щипицина “Жанровый статус сетевого комментария. Вестник Башкирского университета. 2015. Т. 20. №2. С 528-532.

⁸ file:///C:/Users/i7/Downloads/Creative_Commentary_As_A_Type_Of_Media_Language.pdf. Retrieved on: 19.05.2025

⁹ Э.Н.Землянская, Н.М.Королева “Функциональные характеристики речевого жанра «читательский отклик»”⁹ Научная статья /Russian linguistic bulletin 2 (26) 2021. С: 12-15.

According to our observations, although the research works of the above-mentioned scholars have conducted scientific research on Internet communication and its main component, Internet comments, there are almost no linguistic classifications of it as a genre, it is worth recognizing that they have thoroughly studied the specificity of the semantics of the term under study. It is worth noting that attempts to classify comments in linguistic terms are fundamentally different from literary studies. As an example, we can cite the article of the linguist V.I. Karasik, studying the commentary as a genre of speech, in which he classifies the commentary according to the subject and methodological function of the text: theological, legal, historical, political, philological, cultural, etc. In this case, the researcher takes into account the types of speech: everyday, legal and scientific commentary. Such a philological view of commentary as a holistic phenomenon allows us to propose the creation of a descriptive typology, emphasizing the researcher's juxtaposition of journalistic commentary, remark-commentary, and academic commentary¹⁰.

In this article, we support the above classification, but we have found it appropriate to classify it using several additional criteria. According to this, the internet comments:

- a) **According to topic** (scientific, political, popular),
- b) **According to gender** (female comments, male comments and neutral comments),
- c) **According to age** (children and adolescents, young men and women (approximately 18-25 years old) and adults (over 25 years old)
- d) **According to whether the commentator is known or unknown:** (personally known comments, anonymous comments, pseudonymous comments);
- e) **According to the nature of the evaluative**, they are initially divided into two types: positive and negative comments.

Each of the mentioned criteria can be a large object of research. We will certainly address them in detail in our future research. However, in this article we want to focus on the types of comments according to their evaluative indicators. As we all know, comments are not just opinions left under some content, post or blog on social networks or online platforms, but also express the individual views of the author, his subjective (good or bad) assessment.

According to **the evaluative nature**, the commentary speech genre is divided into two types: positive and negative meaning-expressing commentary. In some sources, the evaluative-critical nature of the commentary is likened to the "review" speech genre, which is interpreted as "expressing an opinion about someone or something, giving an assessment of something or a person."¹¹. However, we disagree with the above opinion. The reason is that although both speech genres are forms of expressing opinions about a text or work, they differ from each other in terms of their communicative purpose, style, volume, and depth of meaning.

First of all, we must recognize that the linguistic Sh. Safarov notes the existence of five elements as tools for carrying out the act of evaluation in linguistic activity and that there must be a logical basis for evaluation: "The existence of five elements is mandatory for the occurrence of the act of evaluation, these are the subject, object, basis, standard (sample) and evaluation marker. Evaluation is formed primarily in the subject-object relationship, that is, in the process of determining the importance, significance, quantitative and qualitative distinction of the object by the subject. In this process, the subject compares the property of the object being evaluated with an ideal model or standard and assesses the extent to which it corresponds to or deviates from this standard. Finally, the assessment, which has passed through all the stages of "measurements", occurs through a linguistic sign... also, based on the opinion of the scientist Piotrovskaya, the act of evaluation, which is one of the indicators of

¹⁰Карасик В. И. Комментарий как жанр герменевтического дискурса // Язык, коммуникация и социальная среда. 2009. Вып. 7. С. 32-47.

¹¹Ожегов С.И. Словарь русского языка / Ожегов С.И. – М.: Русский язык, 1984. С 618.

emotional deixis, is a generalization of the illocutionary and perlocutionary tasks through examples¹².

We will try to consider the concept of assessment tools, that is, the five elements listed above, using the example of specific Internet comments in Uzbek language.

"Хилола Хамидовага хурматим зур кушиклари маъноли узиям акилли аёл¹³.

In this comment:

- **Subject** – the person writing the comment, in other words, the commentator (here @ХафизаСафарова-е4м);
- **Object** – Xilola Hamidova (artistic person);
- **Basis** – her songs are meaningful;
- **Eталон** – the fact that she is also an intelligent woman (she always observes the ethical norms expected by the audience, compared to other female singers);
- **Evaluation marker** – the subject's "great respect" for the singer.

In the above comment, the commentator (subject) is the person writing the review. He refers to a specific object (for example, a person or a thing) to perform the act of evaluation. The rationale for the evaluation is the subject's experience, knowledge, or relative views on what he has seen. The standard (sample) is also an important criterion. For example, if someone is reviewing a film, they may be comparing it to other films or expressing an opinion based on the requirements of the genre.

In the example we gave, in addition to the singer's performance skills, his personality is also evaluated. Finally, at the end of the online comments comes the evaluation mark - this is done through expressions such as good, bad, wonderful, boring (in the comment we gave, "my respect is great") and these elements are always present.

The thoughts of the researcher are true, because the elements listed above are involved in the emergence of the evaluative sign, and the evaluation can simultaneously reflect the feelings of the subject (illocutive aspect) and influence the listener (perlocutionary aspect). Below we will consider this aspect through several examples.

A) illocutionary aspect:

1. @AsliddinRasulov-18u: Эй тавба кандай махоратли шоир уезган Баходир ака маромига етказиб ижро этибдилар оллох умрини зиёда килсин хаяжондан кузларимга еш келди жуда зууууууу¹⁴. (Oh my god, what a talented poet, Bahadir aka, wrote this and performed it to its full potential. May God bless his life. My eyes welled up with emotion. It's so great).

2. @IbodotTursunboyeva: Juda go'zal shahar. Allohim bizlarga ham o'sha joylarga borib dam olish nasib qilsin¹⁵. (It's a very beautiful city. May God grant us the opportunity to visit those places and relax).

3. @ХанигулШерматова: Иии шоира опа сиз вапшим кичкина курнасиз

¹⁶. (Sister Shaira, you are such a beautiful little girl, Congratulations, sister, look even younger in 40 years).

B) The perlocutionary aspect is manifested in the following situations.

¹² Сафаров Ш. Прагмалингвистика. - Т.: «Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси» state scientific publishing house, 2008. 204–р.

¹³ <https://youtube.com/watch?v=nKM2bM2BLBU&lc=Ugxvpez63vFAOfAvoOp4AaABAg&si=vHO6gW8uDnaUmm-g>. Retrieved on: 12.06.2025.

¹⁴ <https://youtube.com/watch?v=PX-rQzvje5o&lc=UgzBAMtE5cfNqWEKvc14AaABAg&si=zyLWSK5ZKdollzI>. Retrieved on: 18.05.2025.

¹⁵ https://youtube.com/shorts/wIK9C6eS9M0?lc=Ugz5jxkH0tehkle_BnB4AaABAg&si=67gX7co6w9aW77oQ. Retrieved on: 18.05.2025.

¹⁶ <https://youtube.com/shorts/JC5byuDvBI?lc=UgzM7NrzY91UCVajGxB4AaABAg&si=Nfy8nwUrSRAb-e89>. Retrieved on: 18.05.2025.

1. **In positive evaluative comments**, the perlocutionary aspect is manifested in cases where the author of the post or content is encouraged through positive comments. Such support from followers encourages the post owner to create more such content in the future, that is, it exerts its perlocutionary effect.

Example: Katta bir dars bo'ladigan kino bo'lipdi hamma kelinlar ko'rib o'tgan kunlariga bir nazar soldi adashmasam ijodkorlarga raxmat¹⁷. (It was a movie that taught a great lesson. All the brides watched it and looked back on their days. If I'm not mistaken, thanks to the creators). (from Facebook)

2. **Negative comments**, which express criticism and disapproval from the commentator, cast doubt on the reliability of the information presented in the content and encourage other internet users to be suspicious as well.

Example: Бекорларни 5 тасини айтибсиз , узимизни таомларга хеч қайси таом етмайди. Узбек таомлари энг зор !!!¹⁸ (You've said a bunch of nonsense. Uzbek food is the best!!!). (from Facebook conversations).

3. **In ironic comments**, the author is indirectly criticized, but not directly attacked.

Example: Duo qilaylik ILOHIM SHU QIZGA FAROSAT BER ALLOHIM 🙏🙏🙏¹⁹ (Let's pray, O GOD, GIVE THIS GIRL WISENESS, O GOD).

4. **In neutral comments**, the reviewer gives constructive feedback to the author, but does not criticize harshly. This type of feedback can motivate the author to create better content.

Example: Ajoyib sifatli multfilm chiqibdi, yashanglar! Faqat iltimos imloga etiborli bo'linglar "shoxobcha" emas "shaxobcha" bo'ladi²⁰. (A great quality cartoon has been released, enjoy! Just please pay attention to the spelling, it's "shaxobcha" not "shoxobcha".)

Evaluative comments define the dynamics of online communication and enrich the process of exchange of ideas. Extralinguistic tools (emoji, punctuation marks, font changes) also play an important role in their formation.

1. Comments expressing the meaning of **positivity**, in turn, reveal the following different types of pragmatic content:

a) **Praise:** a comment expressing high respect and honor for the message being conveyed by the author:

1) @MatlubaAbdulayeva: Ассалому алейкум, бу жаноб докторга борган сари хурматим ошади, оила докторлик ва санъат, ҳаммасини қандай епларканлара. Ажабо, ҳаммамизга ҳам шундай шижоат жўшқинлик берсин аллоҳим, тасанно²¹. (Assalamu alaikum, I have more and more respect for this doctor, family, doctorate and art, how they manage it all. Amazing, may Allah grant us all such courage and enthusiasm, thank you);

2) @footbal_pg: Kuni bilan eshityapman. Juda ajoyib satrlar, musiqa va ovoz uyg'unligi bo'libdi. Gap yo'q 🎵🎵🎵²². (I listen to it every day. It's a wonderful harmony of lines, music and voice. Say no more);

b) **Panegyric:** A speech that praises the qualities and merits of a person or group of people. For example, a positive comment under a blogger's helpful content...

¹⁷ https://youtube.com/watch?v=KFggnHYy9MY&lc=UgzwfZ5gPeeeJ1Xd54t4AaABAg&si=KEC_MbZOjwX1gqv8.

Retrieved on: 13.05.2025

¹⁸ <https://youtube.com/shorts/1Hijt5oZAuo?lc=UgzdMw3YmmeNS3NjTCx4AaABAg&si=t6X4UaVRC7DNfael>. Retrieved on: 10.05.2025.

¹⁹ <https://youtube.com/shorts/4McamYd5DhE?lc=Ugym5if-l-u4mlqQen94AaABAg&si=bPBIEFGYuMTM1fwa>. Retrieved on: 13.05.2025.

²⁰ <https://youtube.com/watch?v=lb3jph96gD8&lc=Ugw2keJ14nCiAMWt-7B4AaABAg&si=JLTGhufHXv hvfch>. Retrieved on: 21.05.2025

²¹ <https://youtube.com/watch?v=fX3np27kZrk&lc=UgzZGOusuVGc1wCvwTV4AaABAg&si=8KSakJkpP9tpKi34>. Retrieved on: 10.05.2025.

²² <https://youtube.com/watch?v=fX3np27kZrk&lc=Ugy2URxgujMED4dkqD54AaABAg&si=i2RFpYkjuH6B6evfQ>. Retrieved on: 10.05.2025.

Example: Sarvarbek tashakkurlarim. Tarjimalaringizni o'qib, mazza qilayapman. Telegram kanalimga olib joylayapman ham. Rozi bo'ling. Yana yangilarini kutib qolamiz; (Thank you, Sarvarbek. I am reading and enjoying your translations. I am also posting them on my Telegram channel. I hope you agree. We look forward to more new ones.) (from Facebook conversations).

c) **Congratulatory:** A comment congratulating an individual or group on a specific achievement or event.

1) Men uchun yasha, filmidan keyin bu aktrizamizni mahoratiga tan berdim juda zo'r ijro etilgan, (After the movie "Live for Me", I recognized this actress for her talent. She performed very well (A comment written about Uzbek actress Sitora Alimjonova));

2) Yurt uchun xayrli ishlar bilan charchamang! (May your good deeds for the nation never tire you);

3) Baraka topsinlar ! Juda bir chiroyli ishlardan bopti (from Facebook conversations);

d) **Forecast:** Expresses good wishes and hope for future success.

2. Comments that express a **negative** connotation are considered critical or disparaging opinions about the information provided by the author and are classified as follows:

1. **Critical comments** - point out a specific error or flaw.

For example: Укажон бу сенга хотинлик килолмайди саломни билмайди 😞😞😞😞²³
(For example: Brother, this woman can't be your wife, she doesn't know how to greet people);

2. **Aggressive or offensive comments** – directed against a person, usually based on emotion.

For example: Нафси бузук Хайитта улар бунака Хотинди уман кераги йок Нафсинга ут тушкуп²⁴ (“A man with no control over his desires... Acting like this during Eid. Such a woman is of no value. May your lust burn you.”)

3. **Ironical comments** - do not directly criticize, but express a negative opinion through irony. For example:

a) Artur Grigaryan Fazogir 😂

Yuri Gagarin Bokschi 😂

Bu bog'cha opa Tarixchi 😂²⁵ (Arthur Grigaryan astronaut,
Yuri Gagarin boxer

This kindergarten teacher historian);

b) Хеч бир болани эсида колмасин илохим²⁶ (May no child remember this, God willing);

4) **Trolling comments.** This type of comment, also known as “Negative-ignore” on social media, is written with multiple purposes to spread negative attitudes among the audience (such as provocation, discrimination, or causing conflict between the government and the people). The purpose of trolls can take different forms on different platforms. The linguistic characteristics of trolling comments are manifested in the following.

1. Speech effect;

2. Clear and concise syntactic devices;

3. Means of expressing positive and negative;

²³ <https://www.youtube.com/@llyos-o2s>. Retrieved on: 12.06.2025.

²⁴ <https://youtube.com/shorts/BV-z0zIXc-0?lc=UgxBdwfDih7Hw4-HH394AaABAg&si=1A83C8Hsgms1A3J->. Retrieved on: 13.05.2025.

²⁵ <https://youtube.com/shorts/BiGT84CByb4?lc=Ugz5DsTewwqdiUgoDt4AaABAg&si=zsE8c0a8D-buUt77>. Retrieved on: 13.05.2025.

²⁶ https://youtube.com/shorts/BiGT84CByb4?lc=Ugzg_eZQ6RruBhkVe2l4AaABAg&si=uMdaK-R4K0ZHN0Ud. Retrieved on: 13.05.2025.

4. Effective use of Internet slang;
5. Exaggeration;
6. Irony and sarcasm;

Troll comments are difficult to identify. However, such comments are usually provocative, manipulative and discriminatory in nature, and are intended to create controversy or controversy. Trolling comments include phrases such as **stupid, how stupid, naughty, idiot, idiot, who asked your opinion, what happened, another old story, everything is going according to the script, you can't trust them, everything is agreed upon, everything is sold, you will never change, it was a very fair decision: we cried a lot as a family, traitors...** as well as memes, gifs and mocking stickers. In cyberspace, such trolls' comments can be considered one of the main factors in creating a negative atmosphere among the public.

In the article "The Genre of Internet Commentary: An Axiological Aspect" co-authored by Russian linguists Ye.Yu.Viktorova and K.V.Panteeva, the situation of evaluation through negative and positive comments in the discourse genre of Internet commentary is analyzed. According to the observations presented in the article, negative comments are more numerous than positive ones. According to the available evidence, it is emphasized that the influence of the anonymity factor on the more accurate expression of negativity is significant, and the influence of anonymity on the writing of negative comments is explained as follows.

- The desire of many users in Internet communication to stand out from other commentators.

- leads to more frequent use of negative evaluation and more specific ways of expressing it:

- communication gives users more freedom to express their opinions. Because in most cases, personal opinions are left in the comments

- Anonymity in cyberspace creates a favorable environment for ignoring and criticizing the ideas of others during communication.

The attitudes in the analyzed Internet comments lead to different ways of expressing negative evaluations:

No	Tools that generate negative comments	Examples of negative comments
1	Adjectives that express the meaning of negativity	Words like stupid, ignorant, absurd, wicked, hypocritical, and scoundrel, traitors
2	Metaphors	Tuzsiz, g'iybat post ekan, essiz sarflangan vaqt (A useless, gossipy post is a waste of time) ²⁷ . Coffin on wheels! Grob na kolësax! (abot motorbike) ²⁸ .
3	Rhetorical exclamations	Voy tinib tinchimagan odamlar-ey nimalarni o'ylab topishadiya, ey... hayron qolasanda ko'p odamlarni qilgan ishlariga... shu tinchlik bermasa kerak-da shunaqa befoyda ishlarni qilmaguncha... ²⁹ (Oh, the restless people - what do they think, oh...

²⁷<https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1EG9sfnP6m/>. Retrieved on: 07.03.2025.

²⁸<https://www.facebook.com/share/r/15yaK4uNBv/>. Retrieved on: 01.04.2025

²⁹<https://www.facebook.com/share/v/1ATmrm7sWU/>. Retrieved on: 01.04.2025

		You'll be surprised at what they've done to so many people... They probably won't give you peace until they do such useless things...)
4	Rhetorical questions	Ёмон курган нима овкатиз бор сингилжон 😂😂😂 ³⁰ (As if you ever say no to food (from youtube comments);
5	Neologisms	Ухшамаган пранк 😂 ³¹ (Failed prank)
6	Vulgarisms	Prosta dayus 😞 ming afsus ³² (Unjealous man);
7	Barbarisms	2 та дармайетти кордим холос ³³ (I just saw two useless things, that's all).

From the above, we can conclude that there are several effective methods for studying the evaluative functions of Internet users in the process of mutual communication, and we tried to study them using the example of positive and negative comments. This classification method helps to deeply analyze the reactions, opinions and subjective attitudes of social network users, as well as the formation of social consciousness in cyberspace.

List of used literature:

1. U.U.Mahmudova "Ijtimoiy tarmoq diskursining xususiyatlari" Ta'limda raqamli texnologiyalarni tadbiq etishning zamonaviy tendensiyalari va rivojlanish omillari Conference No. 39, Volume 1, January - 2025. Pages 45-51.
2. А.В.Вовкула "Интерактивная форма коммуникации в медиадискурсе". Вестник Челябинского государственного университета. 2015. № 10 (365). Филология. Искусствоведение. Вып. 95. С. 32-38.
3. А.С.Трач "Особенности использования письменной речи сети интернет" Известия ЮФУ. Технические науки. С: 34-39. file:///C:/Users/i7/OneDrive/Desktop/osobennosti-ispolzovaniya-pismennoy-rechi-v-seti-internet.pdf.
4. Д.А.Рустамов "Интернет мулоқотининг ўзига хос жиҳатлари" Сўз санъати халқаро журнали | Международный журнал искусство слова | International journal of word art №3 | 2020. 213-220- б.
4. Э.Н.Землянская, Н.М.Королева "Функциональные характеристики речевого жанра «читательский отклик»" Научная статья /Russian linguistic bulletin 2 (26) 2021. С: 12-15.
5. Е. Ю. Викторова, К. В. Пантеева. Жанр интернет-комментария: аксиологический аспект. Научная статья. 2023. Т. 18, № 1 (37). С.66-73.
6. Карасик В. И. Комментарий как жанр герменевтического дискурса // Язык, коммуникация и социальная среда. 2009. Вып. 7. С. 32-47.

³⁰ https://youtube.com/watch?v=VH_EWNApoto&lc=UgyZpDPMYPXeuNb9Krl4AaABAg&si=s-zsXBFun553DEJe. Retrieved on: 13.05.2025.

³¹ https://youtube.com/shorts/3fd0kPyCa_Q?lc=UgxHvtjdFFbhHKKkiEl4AaABAg&si=oDiR_PIOphxqFVxo. Retrieved on: 13.05.2025.

³² <https://youtube.com/shorts/bvoDX-FIsbM?lc=UgzT77Sn20byrtjwf1B4AaABAg&si=IPUPr9AUtCG3-OtX>. Retrieved on: 13.06.2025.

³³ https://youtube.com/shorts/uaSz5hBXn78?lc=Ugy7uEa3P7Qvr_hUWu14AaABAg&si=AwbHSt-T499YhQIt. Retrieved on: 13.06.2025.

7. Л. Ю. Щипицина “Жанровый статус сетевого комментария. Вестник Башкирского университета. 2015. Т. 20. №2. С 528-532.
8. Н. В. Зудилина “Особенности проявления интерактивности интернет-сообществ” Ученые записки Таврического национального университета им. В. И. Вернадского Серия «Философия. Культурология. Политология. Социология». Том 24 (63). 2011. № 3-4. С. 143-152. <file:///C:/Users/i7/OneDrive/Desktop/osobennosti-proyavleniya-interaktivnosti-internet-soobschestv.pdf>.
9. Ожегов С. И. Словарь русского языка / Ожегов С. И. – М.: Русский язык, 1984. С 618.
10. Сафаров Ш. Прагмалингвистика. - Т.: «Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси» давлат илмий нашриёти, 2008. 204– б.
11. Ш. Ҳ. Шаҳобиддинова, Ш. Х. Юлдашева “Интернет мулоқот ва унинг тадқиқига доир айрим мулоҳазалар” Илмий хабарнома, АДУ, №2 2018 йил . 85-88- б.
12. file:///C:/Users/i7/Downloads/Creative_Commentary_As_A_Type_Of_Media_Language.pdf.
13. <https://youtube.com/watch?v=nKM2bM2BLBU&lc=Ugxvpez63vFAOfAvoOp4AaABAg&si=vH06gW8uDnaUmm-g>.
14. <https://youtube.com/watch?v=PX-rQzvje5o&lc=UgzBAMtE5cfNqWEKvc14AaABAg&si=zyLWSK5ZKd0IzZI>. Murojat sanasi: 18.05.2025.
15. https://youtube.com/shorts/wIK9C6eS9M0?lc=Ugz5jxkH0tehkle_BnB4AaABAg&si=67gX7co6w9aW77oQ.
16. <https://youtube.com/shorts/JC5byuDuVBI?lc=UgzM7Nrzy91UCVajGxB4AaABAg&si=Nfy8nwUrSRAb-e89>.
17. https://youtube.com/watch?v=KFggnHYy9MY&lc=UgzwfZ5gPeeJ1Xd54t4AaABAg&si=KEC_MbZ0jwX1gqv8.
18. <https://youtube.com/shorts/1Hijt5oZAuo?lc=UgzdMw3YmmeNS3NjTCx4AaABAg&si=t6X4UaVRC7DNfael>.
19. <https://youtube.com/shorts/4McamYd5DhE?lc=Ugym5if-I-u4mlqQen94AaABAg&si=bPBIEFGYuMTM1fwa..>
20. https://youtube.com/watch?v=lb3jpH96gD8&lc=Ugw2keJ14nCiAMWt-7B4AaABAg&si=JLTGhufHXv_hvfch.
21. <https://youtube.com/watch?v=fx3np27kZrk&lc=UgzZG0usuVGc1wCvwTV4AaABAg&si=8KSAKJkpP9tpKi34..>
22. <https://youtube.com/watch?v=fx3np27kZrk&lc=Ugy2URxgujMED4dkqD54AaABAg&si=i2RFpYKJuHB6evfQ>.
23. <https://www.youtube.com/@llyos-o2s>.
24. <https://youtube.com/shorts/BV-z0zIXc-0?lc=UgxBdwfDIh7Hw4-HH394AaABAg&si=1A83C8Hsgms1A3J->
25. <https://youtube.com/shorts/BjGT84CByb4?lc=Ugz5DsTewwqdiiUgoDt4AaABAg&si=zsE8c0a8D-buUt77>.
26. https://youtube.com/shorts/BjGT84CByb4?lc=Ugzg_eZQ6RruBhkVe2l4AaABAg&si=uMdaK-R4K0ZHN0Ud.
27. <https://www.jeffbullas.com/the-6-critical-types-of-social-media-comments-you-must-plan-for/>.

28. <https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1EG9sfnP6m/>.
29. <https://www.facebook.com/share/r/15yaK4uNBv/>.
30. <https://www.facebook.com/share/v/1ATmrm7sWU/>.
31. https://youtube.com/watch?v=VH_EWNApoto&lc=UgyZpDPMYPXeuNb9Krl4AaABAg&si=s-zsXBFun553DEJe
32. https://youtube.com/shorts/3fd0kPyCa_Q?lc=UgxHvtjdFFbhHKkkiEl4AaABAg&si=oDiR_PlOphxqFVxo.
33. <https://youtube.com/shorts/bvoDXFIsbM?lc=UgzT77Sn20byrtjwf1B4AaABAg&si=IPUPr9AUtCG3-OtX>.
34. https://youtube.com/shorts/uaSz5hBXn78?lc=Ugy7uEa3P7Qvr_hUWu14AaABAg&si=AwbHSt-T499YhQIt.

